

Wear Behavior of Thermoplastic Polymer-Filled PTFE Composites

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A variety of new PTFE composites has been produced which demonstrates unique wear and mechanical properties when compared to inorganic PTFE composites. Salient lubrication properties include exceptionally low wear of both the composite and counterface and low coefficient of friction. These results are interpreted both in terms of the mechanical properties and morphology of the composites. Composites discussed emphasize binary systems with polyoxybenzoate and polyphenylene sulfide. In the case of polyphenylene sulfide, three component systems are also considered. It will be demonstrated that thermoplastic polymer filled PTFE composites extend the range of utility of PTFE bearing and roller applications.

INTRODUCTION

Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) is often prepared as a composite in order to reduce wear rate. It is well established that the introduction of a variety of particulate fillers can decrease wear 500-1,000 fold (1), (2). At the same time, the unique frictional characteristics of the PTFE matrix are maintained. Due to the extreme thermal stability requirement imposed by PTFE processing, fillers utilized are predominantly inorganic materials. Examples are glass fiber, bronze, molybdenum disulfide, and carbon-graphite. The broad utilization of these materials despite high material cost is predicated on high performance and low maintenance. Bearings, slides, piston rings, etc., are fabricated from PTFE composites for use in a wide range of chemical and thermal service.

The introduction of inorganic fillers to a PTFE matrix has one conspicuous drawback. The authors consider PTFE as a lamellar solid with low surface energy (11), (12). It has been proposed that transfer of a thin film of polymer to the metal mating surface occurs by removal of lamellar crystalline wedges (13), with virtually no abrasion of the metal. Particulate inorganic fillers introduce an abrasive component in mating surface interaction. Wear

of the metal mating surface becomes an important component in the overall performance of the wearing couple. At the same time, it is interesting to note that the more effective fillers, insofar as PTFE composite wear is concerned, have the most abrasive effect on counterface.

This investigation was conducted to attempt the optimization of wear characteristics in the total system—PTFE composite and metal counter-surface. The mechanism for wear reduction in PTFE composite was examined. Current theories for wear reduction were not regarded as satisfactory (3). In particular, high composite thermal conductivity and compressive strength do not appear to be able to account for the primary reductions in wear rate. Counter examples: A 60 percent bronze-filled PTFE has twice the compressive strength and twice the thermal conductivity of 25 percent glass fiber-filled PTFE. Yet the two have similar wear rates. It has been demonstrated that shear strength has no correlation with wear rate in filled fluorocarbons. After this investigation provided what appeared to be a more acceptable explanation of composite wear characteristics, new composites were formulated and evaluated for wear behavior.

RESULTS

Scanning Electron Micrographs (SEMS) were prepared by metallizing specimens with 150-200 Å gold. The primary electron beam was 25 kv, 35,000 cps. The scan for identification of PPS polymers utilized secondary x-ray emission from the sulfur atom. SEMS were taken from above and perpendicular to the wear surface. The latter was obtained by microtoming directly through the wear surface. All pictures are 300X.

Experimental details of wear testing have been discussed in previous publications (4), (5). Wear is determined on a thrust washer (face ID 1.000 in-1.005 in, face OD 1.120 in-1.125 in) operating at 150 ft/min under 33.3 psi load and mating against 12-15 rms SAE 1040 steel. It has been found that, in cases where PV limit is not approached,

wear is relatively independent of velocity and loading (ϕ). Wear ("K" factor) appears as a dimensioned constant 10^{-10} in³ min/ft/lb/hr since the term for hardness has been omitted. Three test specimens were utilized for each value. Results were reproducible within 10 percent. LPV is determined on half-journal bearings 1.000 in. ID, 0.060 in. wall and 1 in. in length. Specimens are step-loaded at various test velocities (10 ft/min, 100 ft/min, and 1,000 ft/min). The last loading where the specimen maintains equilibrium without demonstrating increased torque or temperatures is designated the limiting pressure velocity (LPV) for that specific velocity. All test results were reproducible with 1,000 lb-fpm.

Figures 1 and 2 are SEM's of an unfilled PTFE wear surface. Figure 1 is a direct view of the wear surface. Figure 2 was obtained by microtoming a section perpendicular to the wear surface. The top edge is the wear surface, while the front face is an internal view of the sample. The mating surface is smooth and wear debris is generated as a fibrous film. This contrasts sharply with the SEM's of bronze and glass fiber filled PTFE shown in Figs. 3 through 6. The unfilled PTFE is wearing at 1,000 times the rate of the filled materials and wear fragments are quickly removed. The surface of the filled materials is littered with small patches of films and fibers. At the same time, the overall profile of the wear surface is actually quite smooth. Macroscopically, the surface has a glazed appearance. It can also be observed that there is virtually no adhesion between the fillers and the resin. The particles are held in the composite only by mechanical forces.

While virgin PTFE exhibits an extremely high rate of wear, composite formulations containing an optimum

loading, result in an almost identical low wear rate. The chief exceptions to this are composites which contain lamellar lubricants such as graphite or molybdenum disulfide. With these fillers, very little reduction in wear is

Fig. 2—Wear surface of virgin PTFE, perpendicular view 300X

Fig. 1—Wear surface of virgin PTFE 300X

Fig. 3—Wear surface of 60 percent bronze-filled PTFE 300X

Fig. 4—Wear surface of 60 percent bronze-filled PTFE, perpendicular view 300X.

Fig. 6—Wear surface of 25 percent glass-fiber-filled PTFE, perpendicular view.

Fig. 5—Wear surface of 25 percent glass-fiber-filled PTFE

observed. If wear reduction is observed, the rate is still not as low as achieved with nonlamellar fillers. In every composite with reasonable wear properties, the coefficient

of friction of the composite approaches very closely that of PTFE.

If a low level of carbon-graphite filler is incorporated into PTFE, the initial wear rate is almost identical to unfilled PTFE. The wear rate decreases with time until a value "typical" for the composite is achieved (10). Most investigators ignore "break-in" observations. With the higher loadings typically encountered, this effect is not observable. The results simply suggest the necessity of exposing the filler on the surface. The formation of copper fluoride on the surface of bronze-filled PTFE also indicates that the filler is exposed and takes an active part in wear activities. It has also been shown that configuration of a filler has no effect on the wear rate of a composite, although it does effect the wear rate of the counterface (7).

An explanation of fluorocarbon composite wear phenomena consistent with previously reported data and the SEM's can be constructed. When a composite is first placed in rubbing contact, the PTFE abrades rapidly in a manner analogous to the neat resin. A portion of this and subsequent PTFE resin debris is transmitted to the mating surface (7), (8), (9). As the filler reaches the surface, it interrupts the transfer of large films and fibers. The fillers have a greater modulus and shear strength than PTFE. The fillers bear most of the load and further protect the PTFE from wear contact. As PTFE debris is generated, it behaves as a boundary lubricant between the filler and the mating surface. This accounts for the fact that the coefficient of friction of the composite is essentially the same as PTFE and not the average of the components. As the authors regard PTFE as lamellar, the inclusion of lamellar

lubricants, like molybdenum disulfide and graphite which increase the modulus and thermal conductivity of the compound, do not reduce wear rate since they are subject to the same shear forces. They are not available on the surface of the composite as load bearing components since the lateral wear motion smooths them.

A selection of fillers to optimize wear properties of PTFE composites was made on the basis of nonlamellar structure and hardness. This contrasts with traditional fillers which were selected for compressive strength and thermal conductivity. High-temperature thermoplastic polymers represent a class of materials conforming to these properties. Among materials including polyimides, polyarylsulfones, polycarbodiimides, polyoxybenzoates, and polyphenylene sulfides, the latter two were found most acceptable. Selection was based on long-term thermal stability, particulate structure and commercial availability.

Poly *p*-oxybenzoate homopolymer is stable up to 800 F, about 90 F above typical PTFE sintering temperatures. The polymer is highly crystalline. It undergoes a crystal-crystal transition at 625 F. It has a coefficient of friction of 0.37. Table 1 tabulates wear and mechanical properties of 10 percent and 25 percent poly *p*-oxybenzoate filled PTFE along with unfilled PTFE and a 15 percent glass fiber filled PTFE.

It is apparent that a filler level at 10 percent poly *p*-oxybenzoate PTFE (FC160), Figs. 7 and 8, is sufficient to provide enough film interruption to give substantially improved wear properties. Higher loadings of poly *p*-oxybenzoate effect little improvement in wear. In fact, the increased interruption of the PTFE matrix results in lower mechanical properties and is manifested in wear characteristics by lower limiting pressure velocity values. Thus, while wear factor is improved from 7 to 5, the limiting pressure velocities are reduced about 25 percent. The most significant values are the low wear on metal mating surfaces.

The 25 percent filled material exhibited mating surface wear of only 0.002 milligrams/hour. This is comparable to unfilled PTFE—0.001 mg/hr and considerably below other filler systems. For example: 60 percent bronze-PTFE—0.007 mg/hr, 5 percent coke flour-PTFE—0.049, 15 percent glass fiber-PTFE—0.030 are all considerably higher. If total wear of both mating surfaces is taken into consideration, the 25 percent poly *p*-oxybenzoate has 1/20 the wear rate of 15 percent glass fiber PTFE.

Polyphenylene sulfide is a crystalline, cross-linkable

Fig. 7—Wear surface of 25 percent polyoxybenzoate-filled PTFE

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF THERMOPLASTIC POLYMER FILLED PTFE

PROPERTY	UNITS	FC100	FC103	FC160	FC161	PDX-4085	PDX-4001	PDX-4949	PDX-4173
Filler type.....			Glass Fiber	Poly oxy- benzoate	Poly oxy- benzoate	PPS	PPS	PPS/Carbon/ MoS ₂	PPS/Carbon/ MoS ₂
Filler %.....	% wt.	0	15	10	25	20	40	50	35
Specific gravity.....		2.15	2.21	2.05	1.91	1.95	1.73	1.84	1.96
Tensile strength*.....	psi	4,500	3,100	2,900	1,800	1,200	1,600	1,200	1,600
Tensile elongation*.....	%	400	300	250	170	100	6	2	75
Compressive strength @.....	psi								
0.2% Offset.....		1,100	1,200	1,270	1,550	2,150	3,925	4,200	2,850
1% Strain.....		630	880	850	1,150	1,175	1,500	1,425	1,250
5% Strain.....		1,750	1,920	1,800	2,300	2,500	4,900	4,725	3,100
Wear (K) factor × 10 ⁻¹⁰	in ³ -min lb-ft-min	5,000	7	7	5	4	7	2	2
Metal mating surface wear..	mg/hr	0.001	0.030	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.001
Dynamic coefficient of friction	@ 33.3 psi 150 fpm	0.05	0.09	0.16	0.13	0.13	0.16	0.12	0.16
Static coefficient of friction..	@ 33.3 psi	0.04	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.08
Limiting PV @									
10 fpm.....		1,200	8,500	16,000	15,000	9,000	11,000	15,000	12,500
100 fpm.....		1,800	10,000	24,000	18,000	9,600	10,800	15,000	11,000
1,000 fpm.....		2,500	12,500	15,000	12,000	7,500	7,500	7,500	7,500

* Test perpendicular to the mold direction.

thermoplastic with a melt point of 529 F. It has a Rockwell hardness of R-123 which is high among plastic resins, but still low compared to the inorganic fillers. The salient property of the polymer is its high compressive and flexural modulus.

Incorporation of PPS into PTFE at 20 percent and 40 percent loadings results in wear rates of 4 and 7 respectively. Figures 9 and 10 are SEMs of the 20 percent PPS filled PTFE. Once again, the film interruption is apparent. In order to determine more exactly the extent of

Fig. 8—Wear surface of 25 percent polyoxybenzoate-filled PTFE, perpendicular view.

Fig. 10—Wear surface of 20 percent PPS-filled PTFE, perpendicular view.

Fig. 9—Wear surface of 20 percent PPS-filled PTFE

Fig. 11—Wear surface of 20 percent PPS-filled PTFE, sulfur x-ray emission.

surface area which is PPS an x-ray scan was made for sulfur. Figure 11 indicates that the PPS occurs as discontinuous patches comprising 25-30 percent of the surface area. The mating surface wear is low for both compounds. Limiting pressure velocity of the compounds is good at low speeds, while at higher speeds it is comparable to other filler systems. The improvement at low PVs is presumably due to the good compressive properties of the compound. All PPS compounds exhibited compressive modulus higher than any filled material previously reported. At high strains, compressive modulus was two to three times as great as bronze-filled materials. An attempt was made to further modify PPS by the addition of carbon-graphite and molybdenum disulfide. This yielded the lowest wear rate and the highest compressive modulus of any PTFE composite tested by the authors' laboratory. The PPS-carbon-graphite-MoS₂ designated PDX-4949 has a wear factor of 2 and removed metal from the mating surface at only 0.002 mg/hr. This is more than a 30-fold reduction in wear (of the total wear couple) when compared to glass-filled PTFE. If lower proportions of total filler are utilized, wear properties are maintained even though compressive strength is reduced. This is demonstrated in the blend designated PDX-4173.

CONCLUSIONS

Several new PTFE composites were prepared in an effort to produce low total wear of both composite and mild steel

mating surface. The formulation of the compounds was predicated on experimental results which suggested that a soft, nonlamellar filler would interrupt PTFE transfer. Composites based on both poly *p*-oxybenzoate and polyphenylene sulfide generated unprecedented low wear rates of the total wear system. These results suggest end use evaluation of the materials where low maintenance and long life are important. In addition, the polyphenylene sulfide composites have extremely high compressive modulus suggesting further evaluation where dimensional stability is a consideration.

REFERENCES

- (1) O'Rourke, J. T., *Machine Design*, 35 (1963).
- (2) Rudner, M. A., *Electrical Manufacturing*, 80 (2) (1955).
- (3) Arkles, B. C., Goodhue, R., and Gerakaris, S., Chapter in "Advances in Polymer Friction & Wear" ed. L. H. Lee, Plenum Press, 1974.
- (4) O'Rourke, J. T., *Modern Plastics*, 42 (1965).
- (5) Theberge, J. E., "ASLE Proceedings—International Conference on Solid Lubrication" SP-3, (1971).
- (6) Archard, J. F. and Hirst, W., *Proc. R. Soc. Lond.*, A 236, 397, (1956).
- (7) Speerchneider, C. V., C.H.L.; *Wear*, 5, 392 (1967).
- (8) Fitzsimmons, V. G. and Zisman, W. A., *NRL Report* 4753, June 1956.
- (9) Pooley, C. M. and Tabor, D., *Proc. R. Soc. Lond.*, A 324, 251 (1972).
- (10) Lontz, J. F. and Kummick, M. C., *ASLE Trans.*, 6, 276, (1963).
- (11) Bassett, D. C. and Davitt, R., *Polymer*, 15, 721, (1974).
- (12) Bunn, C. W. and Cobbold, A. J., R.P.J. *Polymer*, 9, 385, (1958).
- (13) Tanaka, K., Uchiyama, Y., and Toyooka, S., *Wear*, 23, 153, (1973).

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